

Strategies in Creating Learning Centered Classroom and its Management

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ABSTRACT : Present knowledge based society is leading our civilization to its destiny of better and prospective future. Constructivist theory of learning makes us to believe that the learners construct their own knowledge. So, helping the learners for construction of knowledge is now the focus of all educational endeavours in the classrooms. Accordingly, the teaching community is passing through a change in terms of their task. Being guided by the constructivism, teachers are desperately striving for facilitating learning. The teacher's task becomes easier when he can transform his students into a learning community. Greatest satisfaction can be enjoyed by a teacher if he can maintain learning by managing his classroom well and leads his students to achieve the academic goals. This paper tries to highlight the paradigm shift of teaching to learning in classroom; the strategies to create learning centered classroom and the strategies of classroom management those help the teachers to uphold learning in the classroom.

Keywords : Learning community, learning centered classroom, classroom management.

Introduction

“The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classroom” - the very beginning line of the report of the Education Commission (1964-66), chaired by Dr. D.S. Kothari, has an everlasting implication in the teaching-learning process of formal system of education. The teaching-learning process mainly occurs in classroom situation. A classroom is a place where teacher tries to facilitate learning of his students through

teaching or instruction. Therefore importance of classroom is undeniable in teaching-learning process. As a leader in the classroom, teacher can create a favourable learning environment in the classroom. A congenial environment in the classroom helps the learner to participate actively in learning and to cooperate with co learners for maintaining order in the classroom. This mostly depends on the teachers managerial ability, their awareness about classroom management procedures and strategies and

above all adoption and application of these procedures in classroom teaching, because it is inevitable that a well managed classroom is prerequisite in creating learning centred classroom. Wang, Haertel and Walberg (1993), as cited in Marzano and Marzano (2003), demonstrated that among all variables classroom management plays most effective role in student achievement which implies that student can not learn in a chaotic and poorly managed classroom. Now it is an important issue to explore the strategies and role of classroom management in creating learning centered classroom where the environment supports the students to learn and achieve academic goals.

Paradigm Shift : Teaching to Learning in Classroom

The focus of present knowledge based society is the construction of knowledge. The teachers who are engaged in teaching are expected to help the learners in constructing knowledge. In a teaching centered classroom, the focus remains with the transmission of knowledge by the teacher to his student i.e. one way transportation of knowledge from the expert to the novice. But in a learning centered classroom, the focus is on the students' learning, what the students achieve by their own activity and endeavour rather than what the teacher transmits. The paradigm of learning is now shifted from teacher centered to student centered and active learner is now considered more important than a diligent teacher.

Stage et.al. (1998) believe that a movement has already been started to focus on such type of quality teaching that foster active learning, that create environment which helps the student to construct knowledge and enhance quality of learning. To achieve these goals, the teaching

community has to proceed towards creating learning centered classroom. To create a learning centered classroom, a teacher needs to know how students learn, how to develop classroom teaching that can manage the classroom well and promote learning among students.

In constructivism, learning is considered as construction of knowledge assuming that learner in his own way creates, restructures knowledge through his experiences. Knowledge exists in each individual's mind and is shaped by experiences. Individual's knowledge, belief and skill are emphasized in constructivism. According to Fosnot (1996), constructivist learning mainly occur on the basis of four principles - (i) learning depends on existing knowledge of a learner, (ii) new ideas occur as a learner changes and adopts his old ideas, (iii) learning involves inventing ideas rather mechanically accumulating facts, (iv) meaningful learning results when old ideas are reoriented and conclusion about new ideas are reached.

In congruence with the theory of constructivism, Marzano (1992) has identified five 'Dimensions of Learning'. On demonstrating the relationship among these dimensions, he states that a learner having attitudes and perceptions conducive to learning (Dimension 1) and by using effective habits of mind (Dimension 5), performs his first task of acquiring and integrating new knowledge (Dimension 2). It implies that the learner must assimilate new knowledge with what he already knows. Positive attitude and perception play a fundamental role in learning process as these are the filter through which learning occurs. It may be mentioned that negative perception about learner's own ability affects his ability and previous knowledge. The assimilation of new

knowledge and skill is a subjective process of interaction between old and new information. Then the learner develops new knowledge through hard working and effective activities which help him to refine his current knowledge (Dimension 3). The ultimate purpose of acquiring knowledge and skill is to use them in a meaningful way through the process of thinking (Dimension 4).

In a constructivist classroom, the approach of instruction by a teacher is to play a role of facilitator for construction of knowledge and stimulate environment for learning. The learning environment should be cooperative, collaborative and supportive. The democratic environment of a learning centered classroom should have some important component such as shared responsibility, decision making, interactive approach among students, and collaborative involvement of learners which will lead the learners to construct their own knowledge.

Strategies in Creating Learning Centered Classroom

Day (2004,p-135) expresses, " Teachers' perception and experiences of their work conditions- leadership, physical plant, resources, organisational features and relationships - inevitably will affect their attitudes to and practices of teaching and learning." A passionate teacher always tries - for the betterment of his students, to understand the classroom from students' perspectives. In a learning centered classroom, students feel connected with the teachers and co-learners because the teacher shares information with the students instead of providing information to them. By being a leader of a classroom, a teacher always prepares plan and adopts strategies that can create learning in classroom.

Creating positive environment:-

Learner Centered Working Group of the American Psychological Association (1997) has identified 14 learner centered principles which emphasize active and reflective nature of learning. Among these principles, context of learning has been identified as an important one. According to this principle, teachers play a major interactive role with the learner and the learning environment. The classroom environment also has significant impact on student learning. If a teacher believes that the students construct knowledge through interacting with each other and he has to play an interactive role then he should organise his classroom environment in such a way that it becomes a catalyst for constructivist learning. Mc Combs and Whisler (1997) believe that learning occurs best in a positive environment which contains positive interpersonal relationship, comfort and order and in which the learner feels appreciated, acknowledged, respected and validated. Kyriacou (1997) also supported that physical environment plays an important part in involving student and make them attentive. Teachers have to try hard for creating positive environment that contains comfort, order as well as interpersonal relationship.

Seating Arrangement:-

Lambert (1995) believes that flexible seating arrangement as opposed to fixed seating arrangement is necessary pre requisite for an interactive classroom. Flexible seating arrangement is not to provide space; rather physical arrangement of seats is to facilitate collaboration, interaction and for making the classroom learning centered.

Developing Self-efficacy:-

According to Bandura (1994), students' belief about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performances (i.e. perceived self efficacy) determine how they feel, think, motivate themselves and behave. Students with high assurance in their capabilities approach difficult academic task as challenges to be mastered and efficacious outlook fosters intrinsic interest and deep engrossment in the academic activities. Stage et. al. (1998) believe that peer teaching, group project work, observation of other students' models of successful learning, encouraging a students to equate with the peer, writing and presentation of individual as well as group work in the classroom, allowing students to capitalize his personal strength and interests by giving him freedom and choices on using resources help the students to develop self-efficacy and ultimately incorporation of these practices would develop a learning centered classroom.

Using resources:-

To make a classroom learning centered, students should be provided with the information from multiple resources. They must have access to their peers, to the teachers, to the books of library, computer and e-resources. Teacher's role is to identify, locate and gather information to support his students. By equipping himself, a teacher's task is to help his students on the areas those are to explore, how to locate the sources of information and resources and what to gather as information during the course of his teaching and the study of his students. He should also prepare a plan for management of resources, which and how are these to be accessed by the students.

Making students forum:-

In a learning centered classroom, students forum is an important component where small group activity, student- teacher interaction, student-student interaction are to be carried on for sharing information and constructing knowledge. Teacher's role is to plan and manage the activities assigned to the students, arrangement of grouping, students' work space, seating pattern for groups during activities so that proper, methodical and collaborative interaction can be held.

Managing time:-

In a learning centered classroom, using of time properly is very crucial. How much time is to be devoted by the students for an activity needs consideration. Teachers' role is to guide his students about how to use time effectively. Teachers are to manage time and organize his class with planned and structured transition of activities, refocus his students' attention to learning activities by providing learning cues, prevention of occurring much gap time between activities and offering of alternatives to students who are waiting to get started for next activity.

Strategies of Classroom Management

Classroom management is the use of strategies by a teacher to organise the classroom learning environment. In the early 1970s classroom management was considered separate from classroom instruction. Researches in 1980s demonstrated that classroom management and classroom instruction are not separate but intricately interwoven with each other. On defining classroom management Brophy (1999, p-43) says, "Classroom management refers to actions taken to create and maintain a learning environment conducive

to successful instruction (arranging the physical environment of the classroom, establishing rules and procedures, maintaining attention to lessons and engagement in academic activities).”

Kounin, as cited in Brophy (1999), noticed in his research regarding classroom management that effective managers shows some key behaviours, which are (i) Withitness (remaining aware of what is going on all parts of classroom at all time by continuously scanning the classroom); (ii) Overlapping (doing more than one thing at a time); (iii) Signal continuity and momentum during lessons (teaching well prepared and well paced lessons that focus students’ attention by providing continuous academic signal); (iv) Challenge and variety in assignments (encouraging students’ engagement in seatwork by providing assignments at the right level of difficulty). Kounin showed that effective teachers focus on establishing effective learning environment, preparing and teaching lessons and engaging students in their work with proper monitoring by watching students’ behaviour closely, intervening inappropriate behaviour before it becomes a problem, and dealing consistently with misbehaviour and attending to students learning.

In the late 80s, the social constructivist approach in learning remarkably shifted the classroom management paradigm which emphasized on establishing effective learning environment in lieu of maintaining discipline in classroom by controlling behaviour. Rogers and Friedberg (1994) emphasized on both teachers’ general orientation towards managing classroom as well as students and the activities emphasized in their approaches to instruction. They suggested that teachers require adopting the measures which features shared responsibility

and community building. Evertson and Neal (2006 ,p-8) say, “ Learning centered classrooms are much more complex than traditional classrooms in terms of short and long term goals enacted, variety and flexibility of activities offered and opportunities for multiple roles for students and teachers. The need for effective management is critical in all classrooms, but the complexity of learning centered classroom increases the challenges.” To meet the challenges, teachers are to adopt some strategies like building learning community, establishing classroom norms and rules, practicing classroom procedures and managing conflicts which would help the teacher in managing learning centered classroom properly.

Building Learning Community:-

According to Johnson and Johnson (1999), school and classroom management begins with establishing a learning community based on cooperation (i.e. working together to achieve mutual goals). To build a learning community in the classroom, cooperation must be ensured in the classroom. The students should be guided to become a learning group in which the students will learn from each other and become a co-creator of knowledge. The learning group is a unit of a learning community as the family is a unit of a community. There are three aspects identified by Evertson and Neal (2006) in a learning community which are social, moral and academic aspects. Social and moral aspects include understanding of how to respect and rely on others, listen and how to be constructive partners and members. By using these aspects teachers can explore academic aspects of learning community by engaging students in different learning activities and problem solving

tasks. Successful building of learning community makes the teacher's task easy in terms of classroom management.

Establishing Classroom rules and norms :

Classroom rules and norms is another aspect of classroom management which are to be established for ensuring order in classroom. McEwan (2000) believes that developing effective rules and norms are deliberate process which requires careful thought and preparation. The careful construction of rules sets a tone for how classroom interaction will be orchestrated. The teacher has to think what kinds of knowledge, skill and activities required for the students. Then he has to prepare rules and norms so that he can manage his classroom. Shared responsibility lies with the teachers and student for effective establishment of norms and rules. Students must know how to communicate with each other, when and how to move from one place or group to another, what level of noise is permissible for communication, which kind of resources are to be used for performing an activity. During the preparation of norms and rules, a teacher has to keep these aspects in his mind. Regarding the effectivity of rules, McEwan (2000, p-28) comments, "If the rules make sense and the students understand the reasons for the rules, they are more likely to follow the rules. Rules that have reasonable rationale are much easier for teachers to explain and enforce." When teachers carefully and thoroughly work with the students to prepare norms and rules which reflect common vision and interest, then students consistently conduct themselves in appropriate ways which ultimately mirrors a well managed learning centered classroom.

Practice of Procedures:

Success of building a learning community and establishing rules and norms depends on how the classroom procedures are practicing by the students. In a participating learning community, the practice of classroom procedure is a complex one as it includes using of variety of resources, moving around the room, participating in multifarious activities such as discussion, sharing knowledge, locating sources for project work, writing of reports, presentation of reports etc. During the practice of procedures, the teachers should watch and monitor closely the students and emphasize on the understanding of procedures. If the students understand and internalize the procedures, they become successful to behave accordingly. Teachers have to spend much of time at the beginning of the year for introducing, communicating and negotiating the rules for establishing and practicing of procedures. This will help the teachers in the long run in making learning centered classroom as well managed.

Managing Conflict :

According to Johnson and Johnson (1999, p-132), "Conflict is the moment of truth within any community. It is almost paradoxical that the more committed members are to the community's goals and the more caring and committed the relationship among members, the more frequent and intense the conflicts". Evertson and Neal (2006) commented that conflict is inevitable part of classroom though the classroom runs effectively and students must learn how to manage conflict. In a participatory classroom, conflict may arise during exchange of ideas among the students, when the students encounter any problems in learning and work responsibly. The responsibility of managing

conflict rests on the learning community but teachers should teach his students how to manage classroom conflict when it occurs. Teachers may adopt some techniques, like how to cooperate and participate in managing classroom conflict, initiate discussion among students to resolve conflicts, hold individual discussion with a particular student. Johnson & Johnson (1999) have also suggested techniques for resolving conflicts like problem solving negotiation and peer-mediation. They believe that conflict resolution procedures enhance the basic values of the classroom and reduce classroom management problems significantly and increase academic achievement as well as long term retention of the academic material which signifies that the classroom community have become learning centered.

Conclusion

Teaching is considered one of the deferential jobs in knowledge driven society. All teachers are tied in a thread when they desire to help their students to reach their maximum potential. On the advent and advancement of constructivism, it is considered that teaching becomes worthwhile when it leads the students to become a learning community. Students construct their knowledge and teachers' task is to facilitate his students' learning. This is more complex task and more important than ever what teachers did. The teachers have to adopt some important strategies those create their classroom learning centered. But to sustain learning in the classroom, classroom management is the key factor to be looked out. There are a number of techniques under broad categories of strategies like building learning community, establishing rules & norms, practicing procedures, managing conflicts on which

teachers are to rely and adopt for proper management of the classroom. With respect to the learners' context, the techniques may vary from situation to situation, so the teachers have to think and evolve new techniques under the broad strategies. In a learning centered classroom, instruction and management are interwoven with each other which make the classroom environment supportive and collaborative to learning. Thus classroom management plays a vital role in making a classroom teaching without learning to teaching with learning. It is to be kept in mind that teaching entails working with human being and people are by nature unpredictable; however by being organised with management procedures, teachers certainly facilitate learning and can lead his students to be a constructor of knowledge which ultimately brings his students in a knowledge creating society of the global village as a knowledge creator citizen.

References

- Bandura, A. (1994). Self - efficacy. In V.S. Ramachandran (Ed.) Encyclopedia of human behaviour (vol 4, pp71-81) New York: Academic press. Retieved from <http://www.des.emory.edn/mfp/BanEncy.html>
- Brophy, J. (1999). Perspective of Classroom Management - Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow in H.J. Friedberg (Ed.) Beyond Behaviourism - Changing the Classroom Management Paradigm,(pp 43-56). Boston: Allyn and Bacon
- Day, C. (2004). A Passion for Teaching, London: Routledge Falmer
- Evertson, C.M. and Neel, K.W. (2006). Looking into Learning-centered classrooms: Implications for classroom Management, (Working paper) National Education Association, Washington D.C. ERIC: ED 495820
- Fosnot, T. (1996). Constructivism : A psychological Theory of Learning, C.T. Fosnot(Ed.) Constructivism-Theory, Perspectives and Practice.

- New York, Teachers College Press, Columbia university Pp-8-33. In J.K.Sood(2006), Knowledge Construction: A Constructivist View of Learning. Journal of Indian Education .vol.31 no.4 (pp. 14-24)
- Johnson, D.W and Johnson, R.T. (1999) The Three Cs of School and Classroom Management Paradigm in, H.J. Freidberg (Ed.), Beyond Behaviourism- Changing the Classroom Management Paradigm. (pp-119-144) Boston: Allyn and Bacon
- Kyriacou, C. (1997). Effective Teaching in Schools-Theory and Practice (2nd ed), Delta Place (UK): Nelson Thornes
- Lambert, N.M. (1995), 'Seating Arrangement'. L.W. Anderson (Ed.) International Encyclopedia of Teaching and Teacher Education, 196-200, Cambridge, U.K:Cambridge University Press. In C.M. Evertson and K.W. Neal (2006), Looking into Learning Centered Classroom-Implication for Classroom Management.
- Learner Centered working Group (1997). Learner Centered Psychological Principles: A Framework for School Reform, American Psychological Association, available at <http://www.apa.org>.
- Marzano, R. J. (1992). A different kind of Classroom: Teaching with Dimensions of Learning, Alexandria, VA, Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development (ASCD).
- Marzano, R.J.and J. Marzano,J.S. (2003). The Key to Classroom Management. Alexandria, VA: Association for supervision and curriculum Development.
- MC Combs and Whisler (1997). Premises of the Learner Centered Model, available at <http://tep.uoregon.edu/workshops/teachertraining/learnercentered/overview/definitions.html>
- Mc Ewan, B. (2000), The Art of classroom Management: Effective Practices for Building Equitable Learning Communities, Columbus: Merrill
- Rogers, C. and Freidberg, H.J.,(1994) Freedom to Learn (3rd ed.) Columbus: Merrill
- Stage et. al. (1998), Creating Learning Centered Classrooms- What Does Learning Theory Have To Say? ERIC: ED 422777.

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